

THE MODEL ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE LAW

(EXPERT DRAFT PROPOSAL)

MAIL v.2.0

April 2024

To follow updates, please scan the QR Code below. Should there be any suggestions, comments, or questions, please feel free to reach out via modelailaw@outlook.com

AIGVERSE

The Drafting Team

ZHOU Hui – Institute of Law, Chinese Academy of Social Sciences

ZHU Yue – Tongji University

ZHU Lingfeng – Xingji Meizu Group Co., Ltd.

SU Yu – People’s Public Security University of China

YAO Zhiwei – Guangdong University of Finance and Economics

WANG Jun – Compliance Tech Research Institute, Southern Finance Omnimedia Group

CHEN Tianhao – Tsinghua University

HE Bo – Internet Law Research Center, China Academy of Information and Communications Technology

HONG Yanqing – Beijing Institute of Technology

FU Hongyu – Key Laboratory of Rule of Law Strategy and Management for Industry and Informatization, Ministry of Industry and Information Technology

WANG Wei – University of Hong Kong

WANG Xiang – ISO/TC 154

LI Xueyao – Shanghai Jiao Tong University

CAO Yanlin – Institute of Medical Information, CAMS & PUMC

WANG Lei – Beijing Institute of Technology

FENG Zixuan – Southwest University of Political Science and Law

DI Xingsi – Guangzhou University

SUN Muyuan – University of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences

ZHU Lingyun – University of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences

JIN Xi’ai – University of Chinese Academy of Social Sciences

The English version was translated and compiled by WANG Wei. This translation is provided solely for reference purposes; the original Chinese version shall prevail as the authoritative text, and the final interpretation shall be based on the original Chinese version.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

CHAPTER I GENERAL PROVISIONS	1
Article 1 – Legislative Basis	1
Article 2 – Scope of Application	1
Article 3 – Governance Principle	2
Article 4 – Human-Centric Principle	2
Article 5 – Safety/Security Principle	2
Article 6 – Principle of Openness, Transparency, and Explainability	2
Article 7 – Principle of Accountability	2
Article 8 – Principle of Fairness and Equality	2
Article 9 – Green Principle (of Sustainability)	3
Article 10 – Principle of Promoting Development and Innovation	3
Article 11 – International Cooperation	3
Article 12 – Competent Authorities	4
Article 13 – Collaborative Governance	4
Article 14 – Legality and Legitimacy	4
CHAPTER II SUPPORT AND PROMOTION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE	6

Article 15 – Development Plan for Artificial Intelligence	6
Article 16 – Construction of Computing Infrastructure	7
Article 17 – Innovation in Algorithms and Foundation Models	7
Article 18 – Supply of Data Production Factors	7
Article 19 – Industrial Development and Application Innovation	8
Article 20 – Professional Talent Cultivation	8
Article 21 – Fiscal and Procurement Support	9
Article 22 – Tax Credit Incentives	9
Article 23 – Pilot Initiatives by State Organs	9
Article 24 – Artificial Intelligence Special Zones and Authorized Legislature	9

CHAPTER III ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE OVERSIGHT

SYSTEM..... 11

Article 25 – Categorized Oversight System	11
Article 26 – Negative-List Oversight System	12
Article 27 – Licensing Conditions for the Negative List	12
Article 28 – Application for Licenses within the Negative List	13
Article 29 – Approval of Licenses within the Negative List	13
Article 30 – Reapplication for Licenses within the Negative List	14
Article 31 – Public Disclosure of License	14
Article 32 – Complaint, Reporting, and Clarification Mechanisms	14
Article 33 – Other Licenses and Registries	15

CHAPTER IV OBLIGATIONS OF AI DEVELOPERS AND

PROVIDERS..... 16

Section 1: General Provisions	16
-------------------------------------	----

Article 34 – Safety Obligations	16
Article 35 – Obligation to Manage Security Vulnerabilities	17
Article 36 – Obligation to Audit	17
Article 37 – Obligation to Remedy and Notify	17
Article 38 – Obligation for Openness and Transparency	18
Article 39 – Obligation for Explainability	19
Article 40 – Obligation for Fairness	19
Article 41 – Risk Management	19
Article 42 – Obligation for AI Ethics Review	20
Article 43 – Obligations of State Organs in Provision and Development	20
Article 44 – Authorized Representatives	20
Section 2: Obligations of Artificial Intelligence Developers	21
Article 45 – Enhanced Obligations for AI Developers on the Negative List	21
Article 46 – Special Obligations for Developers of Foundation Models	21
Section 3: Obligations of Artificial Intelligence Providers	22
Article 47 – Registry Obligations	22
Article 48 – Registry Process	23
Article 49 – Internal Management Systems	23
Article 50 – Termination Mechanism	23
Article 51 – Permission Revocation	24
Article 52 – Enhanced Obligations for Negative-Listed AI Providers	24
Article 53 – Obligations of Platform Operators	24

CHAPTER V COMPREHENSIVE AI GOVERNANCE MECHANISM
..... 25

Article 54 – Responsibilities of the National AI Administrative Authority	25
Article 55 – Committee of Experts on AI Ethics	26

Article 56 – Security Review System	27
Article 57 – Timeframe for Preliminary Procedures	27
Article 58 – Interviewing	27
Article 59 – Innovative Regulation	28
Article 60 – Regulatory Sandbox	28
Article 61 – Officials Responsible for State Organs	28
Article 62 – Law Enforcement	28
Article 63 – Governance through Technology	29
Article 64 – Countermeasures against Foreign Entities	29
Article 65 – Reciprocal Measures	29

CHAPTER VI LIABILITIES 30

Article 66 – General Liabilities	30
Article 67 – Revocation of Negative-List Licenses	30
Article 68 – Discretionary Methods for Administrative Fines	31
Article 69 – Liability for Registry Violations	31
Article 70 – Civil Tort Liability	32
Article 71 – Liability Exemption for Open-Source AI	33
Article 72 – Legal Redress	33
Article 73 – Public Interest Litigation	33
Article 74 – The Interface between Administrative Penalties and Criminal Liabilities .	33
Article 75 – Post-Compliance Non-Prosecution	33
Article 76 – Liability for Failure to Perform Obligations by State Organs	34

CHAPTER VII SUPPLEMENTARY PROVISIONS 35

Article 77 – Military Artificial Intelligence	35
---	----

Article 78 – Definitions	35
Article 79 – Implementation Date	36
Article 80 – Negative-List Disclosure System	36

CHAPTER I

GENERAL

PROVISIONS

ARTICLE 1 – LEGISLATIVE BASIS

To promote the development and innovation of artificial intelligence (AI), regulate the research and development (R&D), provision, and use of artificial intelligence, safeguard national sovereignty, developmental and security interests, and protect the legitimate rights and interests of individuals and organizations, this law is formulated in accordance with the Constitution (of the People's Republic of China).

ARTICLE 2 – SCOPE OF APPLICATION

This law applies to activities related to the R&D, provision, and use of artificial intelligence, as well as the regulation of artificial intelligence, within the territory of the People's Republic of China.

Activities conducted outside the territory of the People's Republic of China that involve the R&D, provision, and use of artificial intelligence, which affect or may affect the national security, public interests, or the legitimate rights and interests of individuals and organizations of the People's Republic of China, are also subject to this law.

ARTICLE 3 – GOVERNANCE PRINCIPLE

The State shall coordinate development and security, adhere to the integration of promoting innovation and governance in accordance with the law, and implement inclusive and prudent regulation.

ARTICLE 4 – HUMAN-CENTRIC PRINCIPLE

In engaging in the R&D, provision, and use of artificial intelligence, parties should adhere to the human-centric principle and be oriented towards intelligent benevolence, ensuring that humanity can always supervise and control artificial intelligence, with the ultimate goal of promoting human welfare.

ARTICLE 5 – SAFETY/SECURITY PRINCIPLE

Those engaged in the R&D, provision, and use of artificial intelligence shall take necessary measures to ensure the safety and security of the artificial intelligence being developed, provided, and used, as well as related network data.

ARTICLE 6 – PRINCIPLE OF OPENNESS, TRANSPARENCY, AND EXPLAINABILITY

Those engaged in the provision of artificial intelligence should adhere to the principle of openness and appropriately label the provided artificial intelligence.

Those engaged in the R&D and provision of artificial intelligence should adhere to the principles of transparency and explainability, taking necessary measures to clarify the purposes, principles, and effects of the artificial intelligence being developed and provided.

ARTICLE 7 – PRINCIPLE OF ACCOUNTABILITY

Those engaged in the R&D, provision, and use of artificial intelligence shall be responsible for their respective activities in R&D, provision, and use.

ARTICLE 8 – PRINCIPLE OF FAIRNESS AND EQUALITY

Those engaged in the R&D, provision, and use of artificial intelligence should adhere to the principle of fairness and take effective measures to avoid unreasonable differential treatment of individuals or organizations.

The needs of special groups such as minors, the elderly, and persons with disabilities should be fully considered in activities related to the R&D, provision, and use of artificial intelligence.

ARTICLE 9 – GREEN PRINCIPLE (OF SUSTAINABILITY)

The State encourages the application of energy-saving and emission-reduction technologies in the R&D, provision, and use of artificial intelligence, promoting the digital ecological civilization that is green and intelligent.

ARTICLE 10 – PRINCIPLE OF PROMOTING DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

The State shall support the construction of artificial intelligence infrastructure, promote the open sharing of public computing power, public data, and other relevant public resources, and encourage individuals and organizations to legally open and share computing power, data, and other relevant resources.

The State shall encourage R&D as well as application of artificial intelligence, protect intellectual property rights in the field of artificial intelligence in accordance with the law, establish a statutory licensing and/or fair use system for intellectual property rights that is compatible with the development of artificial intelligence, and support scientific research and cultural creative activities utilizing AI-generated works. The State Intellectual Property Administration shall, in accordance with the law, formulate supporting rules for the statutory licensing and/or fair use system of artificial intelligence and clarify the mechanisms for the protection of rights and the distribution of benefits of AI-generated works based on the principle of fairness and reasonableness.

ARTICLE 11 – INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION

The State actively engages in international exchanges and cooperation in the field of artificial intelligence. It participates in the formulation and implementation of international rules and standards related to artificial intelligence and promotes the development of an international governance framework and standardization norms for artificial intelligence that have broad consensus.

The State works to improve the mechanisms for talent acquisition, technology import, and technological collaboration in the field of artificial intelligence.

ARTICLE 12 – COMPETENT AUTHORITIES

The China Administration of Artificial Intelligence (CAAI) is the competent authority in charge of the development and administration of artificial intelligence nationwide under the leadership of the central artificial intelligence institution. Other relevant departments and relevant military departments shall, in accordance with the provisions of this Law and applicable laws and administrative regulations, closely cooperate, strengthen coordination, and adequately carry out related work in accordance with the law.

Provinces, autonomous regions, municipalities directly under the Central Government, cities where the people's governments of provinces and autonomous regions are located, cities where special economic zones are located, and larger cities approved by the State Council are responsible for the development and administration of artificial intelligence within their respective jurisdictions in accordance with relevant national regulations.

ARTICLE 13 – COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE

The State shall establish and improve an artificial intelligence governance mechanism involving government administration, corporate responsibility, industry self-regulation, societal oversight, and user self-discipline, promoting collaborative governance among multiple stakeholders.

ARTICLE 14 – LEGALITY AND LEGITIMACY

Entities engaged in the R&D, provision, and use of artificial intelligence must comply with laws and administrative regulations, respect social morality and ethics, and adhere to the following provisions:

- a. Uphold the core values of socialism and refrain from generating content that incites subversion of state power, overthrow of the socialist system, endangers national security and interests, damages the national image, incites separatism, disrupts national unity and social stability, promotes terrorism, extremism, ethnic hatred, discrimination, violence, obscenity, pornography, and other false or harmful information prohibited by laws and administrative regulations;*
- b. Respect intellectual property rights and business ethics, maintain trade secrets, and refrain from using advantages in algorithms, data, platforms, etc., to engage in monopolistic and unfair competitive practices;*
- c. Legally protect the rights and interests of consumers and workers, respect the legitimate rights and interests of others, and refrain from harming the physical*

and mental health of others or infringing upon their rights/interests to likeness, reputation, honor, privacy, and personal information;

CHAPTER II

SUPPORT AND PROMOTION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

ARTICLE 15 – DEVELOPMENT PLAN FOR ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

The State shall improve and implement the New-Generation Artificial Intelligence Development Plan, adhere to the common advancement of AI R&D, product applications, and industrial cultivation, and comprehensively support scientific and technological, economic, social development, and national security.

People’s governments at the provincial level or above should incorporate the development of artificial intelligence into the national economic and social development plans at their respective levels and formulate artificial intelligence development plans as needed.

ARTICLE 16 – CONSTRUCTION OF COMPUTING INFRASTRUCTURE

The State shall establish a public computing power resource supply system for artificial intelligence, promote the construction and utilization of public computing power resource platforms, strengthen the scientific scheduling of computing power, and provide public computing power support for the development of artificial intelligence technology and industry.

It encourages and supports higher education institutions, research institutions, enterprises, and other organizations in constructing AI computing infrastructure. It promotes the market-based transaction of computing power resources, guides various industries to use computing power resources in a rational and orderly manner, and enhances the utilization efficiency of computing power infrastructure.

ARTICLE 17 – INNOVATION IN ALGORITHMS AND FOUNDATION MODELS

The State shall support innovation in artificial intelligence algorithms, encourage the establishment and operation of open-source development platforms, open-source communities, and open-source projects, encourage the establishment of open-source artificial intelligence foundations, and promote the secure and compliant application of open-source software projects.

The State shall establish a personal information handling regime that adapts to the development of foundational models. In the data training phase of foundational models, if the de-identification technology that complies with national standards is adopted after certification, the obligation of personal information handlers may not be assumed.

The State shall legally strengthen the protection of foundational models and foster the innovative development and widespread application of foundational models.

ARTICLE 18 – SUPPLY OF DATA PRODUCTION FACTORS

The State supports the construction of foundational and specialized databases in the field of artificial intelligence. It promotes the efficient aggregation and shared utilization of data resources, expands the scope of public data supply for artificial intelligence applications, comprehensively implements the deployment of a national integrated big data center system, optimizes the layout of data center infrastructure, cultivates data

center clusters, institutionalizes the fair use system of AI training data, and ensures the supply of data production factors in the field of artificial intelligence.

It encourages and guides relevant entities to engage in collaborative R&D of big data and AI technologies. It supports these entities in deeply integrating data with industrial knowledge to develop data products that serve algorithmic design, model training, product validation, and contextual/scenario application.

ARTICLE 19 – INDUSTRIAL DEVELOPMENT AND APPLICATION INNOVATION

The State shall accelerate the transfer and application of key artificial intelligence technologies, promote the integration of technology and innovation in business models, drive the innovation of intelligent products in key areas, actively cultivate emerging artificial intelligence industries, and establish internationally competitive artificial intelligence industrial clusters.

It shall also promote the integrated innovation of artificial intelligence with various industries, carry out pilot demonstrations of artificial intelligence applications in key industries and fields, encourage the scaled application of artificial intelligence, and support the application and promotion of new technologies, new products, new services, and new models in artificial intelligence.

ARTICLE 20 – PROFESSIONAL TALENT CULTIVATION

The State shall support higher education institutions in improving the disciplinary layout and talent cultivation mechanisms in the field of artificial intelligence.

Higher education institutions, research institutions, and enterprises are encouraged to conduct fundamental and theoretical research aimed at addressing major scientific frontiers in artificial intelligence, as well as R&D of key generic technologies, and undertake major technological and industrial innovation projects.

The State shall also support the establishment of innovative project management mechanisms, talent evaluation mechanisms, and incentive mechanisms for the knowledge exchange and technology transfer of scientific and technological achievements, aimed at promoting the development of artificial intelligence.

ARTICLE 21 – FISCAL AND PROCUREMENT SUPPORT

The Central Finance should set up an artificial intelligence subject within its budget and allocate special funds to develop artificial intelligence.

Local people’s governments at or above the county level should, according to actual conditions, allocate special funds to develop artificial intelligence in their financial budgets.

Provincial and local people’s governments, as well as state-owned enterprises and public institutions, shall be encouraged to procure open-source artificial intelligence products and services that conform to national standards.

ARTICLE 22 – TAX CREDIT INCENTIVES

For investments made by artificial intelligence developers and providers in the R&D or procurement of dedicated equipment used for safety governance and other purposes, a tax credit of not less than 30% of the investment amount shall be granted.

The State Council shall stipulate specific preferential tax treatment for the R&D of open-source artificial intelligence.

ARTICLE 23 – PILOT INITIATIVES BY STATE ORGANS

Governmental agencies, public institutions, and other organizations legally endowed with the function of managing public affairs are encouraged to pioneer and pilot the application of artificial intelligence technology in fields such as government services and public management in accordance with the law, giving priority to the procurement and use of safe and reliable artificial intelligence products and services.

ARTICLE 24 – ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE SPECIAL ZONES AND AUTHORIZED LEGISLATURE

The State shall establish artificial intelligence special zones in qualified regions to promote the pioneering and piloting of artificial intelligence innovation and development, facilitate the integration of production, education, research and application of artificial intelligence, and construct a favourable ecosystem for the development of artificial intelligence.

The municipal people's congresses and their standing committees of the locations where artificial intelligence special zones are situated may, in accordance with this Law and based on the practical needs of artificial intelligence innovation and development within the special zones, and in adherence to the provisions of the Constitution as well as the basic principles of laws and administrative regulations, formulate regulations regarding the R&D, provision, and use of artificial intelligence, which shall be implemented within the scope of the artificial intelligence special zones.

The regulations of artificial intelligence special zones may provide flexible provisions to laws, administrative regulations, and local regulations as authorized.

The regulations of artificial intelligence special zones shall be filed with the Standing Committee of the National People's Congress and the State Council; for flexible provisions made to laws, administrative regulations, or departmental rules, the circumstances and reasons for such flexibility shall be explained.

CHAPTER III

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE OVERSIGHT SYSTEM

ARTICLE 25 – CATEGORIZED OVERSIGHT SYSTEM

The State establishes an Artificial Intelligence Negative List, subjecting products and services within the negative list to a licensing oversight system and, where necessary, those outside the negative list to a registry oversight system.

The National AI Administrative Authority, considering the critical role of AI in economic and social development, and the potential risks to national security, public interests, societal stability, environmental protection, the legitimate rights and interests of individuals and organizations, and the economic order, should it be attacked, tampered with, destroyed, or illegally accessed or utilized, shall take the lead in formulating and periodically updating the Negative List for AI products and services.

ARTICLE 26 – NEGATIVE-LIST OVERSIGHT SYSTEM

Prior to conducting R&D or providing services and products that are within the scope of the Artificial Intelligence Negative List, entities must obtain administrative licenses from the National AI Administrative Authority.

Unlicensed activities, or activities that exceed the scope of the granted license for R&D or provision of products and services within the Artificial Intelligence Negative List, are prohibited.

ARTICLE 27 – LICENSING CONDITIONS FOR THE NEGATIVE LIST

Entities applying for a license to conduct R&D, or to provide services and products within the scope of the Artificial Intelligence Negative List, must meet the following conditions:

- 1. Be a legal entity established in accordance with the laws of the People’s Republic of China;*
- 2. The principal person in charge must be a Chinese citizen;*
- 3. Employ full-time personnel with specialized knowledge in quality assurance, safety measures, human oversight, and compliance management that is commensurate with the associated risks;*
- 4. Possess a comprehensive Artificial Intelligence Quality Management System, Network Data Security Management System, and Scientific Ethics Review System;*
- 5. Implement secure and controllable measures to safeguard artificial intelligence technology;*
- 6. Have an emergency response mechanism for artificial intelligence that is proportionate to the associated risks;*
- 7. Possess suitable premises, facilities, and funding that are commensurate with the scale of artificial intelligence R&D, and provision;*
- 8. Comply with other provisions as stipulated by laws and administrative regulations.*

ARTICLE 28 – APPLICATION FOR LICENSES WITHIN THE NEGATIVE LIST

AI developers and providers applying for a license to engage in R&D or provision of AI products and services within the scope of the Negative List must submit the following documentation:

- 1. Application form;*
- 2. Proof of legal entity status, premises, and funding;*
- 3. Verification that the principal person in charge is a Chinese citizen;*
- 4. Credentials of full-time personnel specializing in quality assurance, safety measures, human oversight, and compliance management;*
- 5. Information on the Artificial Intelligence Quality Management System, Network Data Security Management System, Scientific Ethics Review System, and Risk Management System, as well as their implementation status;*
- 6. Artificial Intelligence Safety/Security Assessment Report;*
- 7. Any other documentation as required by applicable laws and administrative regulations.*

ARTICLE 29 – APPROVAL OF LICENSES WITHIN THE NEGATIVE LIST

Upon receiving an application for a license for R&D or provision of AI products and services within the scope of the Negative List, the National AI Administrative Authority must conduct a preliminary review within 10 days.

If, upon preliminary review, it is found that the submitted application materials from the AI developers and providers do not meet the required criteria, the National AI Administrative Authority may request that they supplement or correct the application. If the AI developers and providers do not provide the required supplementary materials or corrections without legitimate reason, the application will be deemed withdrawn.

If the preliminary review establishes that all submitted materials are complete, the National AI Administrative Authority must finalize its review within 45 days of accepting the application, and render a decision either to grant or deny the license. If approved, a license for R&D or provision of AI will be issued to the applicant; if denied, the applicant must be notified in writing with reasons for the denial provided.

Should the National AI Administrative Authority be unable to make a decision after the expiration of the period, an extension of up to 10 days may be granted upon approval by the Head of the National AI Administrative Authority. The reason for such an extension must be communicated to the applicant.

ARTICLE 30 – REAPPLICATION FOR LICENSES WITHIN THE NEGATIVE LIST

The license for R&D or provision of Artificial Intelligence within the scope of the Negative List should specify the duration and scope of the license’s validity.

If activities exceed the scope of the license or if changes in technology, use case scenarios, or target user groups lead to a change in associated risks, AI developers and providers within the scope of the Negative List must reapply for a license for R&D or provision.

Six months prior to the expiration of the license, AI developers and providers within the scope of the Negative List may apply for a renewal of their license for R&D or provision.

Should AI developers and providers within the scope of the Negative List cease their licensed R&D or provision activities, they are required to apply for cancellation of the license with the National AI Administrative Authority within three months from the date of cessation.

ARTICLE 31 – PUBLIC DISCLOSURE OF LICENSE

AI developers and providers within the scope of the Negative List must prominently display the license number in the AI products or services they provide.

ARTICLE 32 – COMPLAINT, REPORTING, AND CLARIFICATION MECHANISMS

Individuals and organizations that discover unlawful activities in the R&D or provision of Artificial Intelligence within the scope of the Negative List have the right to file complaints or reports with the National AI Administrative Authority. The said Authority must promptly verify and address such complaints or reports.

Individuals and organizations that have questions or concerns regarding the activities of R&D or provision of AI within the scope of the Negative List have the right to request

clarification from the National AI Administrative Authority. The said Authority must promptly respond and address the matters raised.

ARTICLE 33 – OTHER LICENSES AND REGISTRIES

Where laws or administrative regulations stipulate that the application of artificial intelligence shall be subject to administrative licensing or registry, AI providers and users shall legally obtain the licenses or complete registries/filings in accordance with the law.

CHAPTER IV

OBLIGATIONS OF AI DEVELOPERS AND PROVIDERS

SECTION 1: GENERAL PROVISIONS

ARTICLE 34 – SAFETY OBLIGATIONS

AI developers and providers must conduct safety/security assessments before deploying AI technologies or introducing them to the market, to mitigate security risks and ensure the safety and robust operation of AI across its entire lifecycle, in alignment with intended objectives. AI developers and providers must maintain safety/security assessment reports for a minimum duration of five years.

AI developers and providers are also obligated to promptly disseminate best practices for security, guiding users toward the safe and correct application of artificial intelligence.

In compliance with the provisions of this law regarding record-keeping and technical documentation, AI developers and providers must ensure traceability, enabling prompt and accurate tracing and pinpointing of issues in the event of incidents, thereby ensuring AI safety.

ARTICLE 35 – OBLIGATION TO MANAGE SECURITY VULNERABILITIES

Relevant organizations and individuals are encouraged to notify AI developers and providers of any security vulnerabilities present in their products or services.

AI developers and providers must fulfill their obligations to manage security vulnerabilities in accordance with relevant regulations, ensure that such vulnerabilities are promptly rectified and reasonably disclosed, and guide and support users in taking preventative measures.

ARTICLE 36 – OBLIGATION TO AUDIT

AI developers and providers must conduct audits in accordance with the relevant national regulations and the requirements of the National AI Administrative Authority. These audits are to verify the compliance of input data, algorithm models, output data, etc., and to review and evaluate whether the activities related to AI products and services adhere to laws and administrative regulations.

ARTICLE 37 – OBLIGATION TO REMEDY AND NOTIFY

AI developers and providers must enhance risk monitoring and, upon identifying any safety defects or security vulnerabilities, must immediately take remedial actions. If AI developers discover any safety incidents with the AI they have developed, they must immediately implement corrective measures and notify AI providers. In turn, AI providers, in accordance with the third provision of this article, must fulfill their notification obligations. When AI providers identify any safety incidents with the AI they offer, they must immediately take action, comply with the notification obligations as outlined in the third provision of this article, and promptly inform the AI developers.

AI providers are required to take immediate corrective actions and, in accordance with national regulations, promptly inform users and report to the supervisory authorities regarding the following matters:

- a. *The occurrence and impact scope of the safety incident;*
- b. *The remedial actions already taken by the AI provider, as well as potential actions that users can take to mitigate harm;*
- c. *The contact information of the AI provider.*

If the measures taken by the AI providers can effectively prevent substantial harm to users, notifying the users may be deemed unnecessary. However, if the National AI Administrative Authority believes the situation could be harmful, it reserves the authority to require the provider to notify affected users.

Upon discovering a safety incident or receiving notification of such from the provider, AI developers should immediately perform an assessment. If the assessment reveals risks that originated during the development stage, the developer must immediately notify other AI providers and temporarily suspend or remove the affected AI products or services until the risks are resolved. Upon receiving such notification, other AI providers must immediately take remedial actions to manage the risks associated with their products and services.

ARTICLE 38 – OBLIGATION FOR OPENNESS AND TRANSPARENCY

AI providers offering AI services that interact with natural persons must, before users engage with the AI, disclose in a concise, clear, and easily understandable manner to the natural persons interacting with the AI products and services that they are interacting with an AI service. However, this does not apply if the natural persons can deduce that they are interacting with an AI from the context of use.

Providers of deep synthesis services in artificial intelligence should, in accordance with national regulations, reasonably mark synthesized content and alert the public to the deep synthesis context.

Prior to the use of artificial intelligence by users, providers should appropriately inform users of the following information:

- a. *The basic principles, intended purpose, and main operating mechanisms of the product or service;*
- b. *Public information on the license or registry of the product or service;*
- c. *The rights and remedies available to the user;*
- d. *Any other information required by laws or administrative regulations.*

AI developers should cooperate with providers to fulfill these obligations above.

ARTICLE 39 – OBLIGATION FOR EXPLAINABILITY

For AI products and services that have a significant impact on individual rights and interests, users of the AI have the right to request explanations from the providers about the decision-making process and methods of the products and services. Users have the right to lodge complaints about unreasonable explanations.

AI providers should take into account factors such as the scenarios and nature of their products and services, as well as the level of technological development in the industry, and promptly respond to users' requests.

AI developers should cooperate with providers to fulfill these obligations above.

ARTICLE 40 – OBLIGATION FOR FAIRNESS

AI developers should take necessary measures during the processes of data handling and labeling, algorithmic model design, development, and validation testing to effectively prevent harmful biases and discrimination.

AI providers should enhance the stewardship of input and output data while providing products and services to effectively prevent harmful biases and discrimination.

ARTICLE 41 – RISK MANAGEMENT

AI providers, taking into consideration factors such as the scenarios, nature, audience, and the level of technological development within the industry, should establish and implement a comprehensive risk management system that spans the entire lifecycle. Prior to the deployment and during the use of their products and services, AI providers must identify potential risks associated with artificial intelligence and implement necessary control measures. AI providers are required to maintain records of risk identification and the measures taken for no less than two years.

AI developers must establish and operate a risk management system throughout the R&D process, including design, data collection and training, model selection, and testing and validation. They should identify risks associated with artificial intelligence and implement necessary control measures. While ensuring the confidentiality of trade secrets, AI developers should cooperate by providing safety/security assessment reports, records of risk identification, and control measures to support AI providers in fulfilling their risk

management obligations for AI services. AI providers must retain records of risk assessments and the measures taken for no less than two years.

ARTICLE 42 – OBLIGATION FOR AI ETHICS REVIEW

When engaging in the R&D or provision of artificial intelligence involving sensitive areas determined by the National AI Administrative Authority, an AI Ethics Review Committee shall be established, and artificial intelligence ethics reviews shall be conducted in accordance with relevant national regulations.

State organs and other organizations with statutory functions of public affairs administration shall conduct artificial intelligence ethics reviews in accordance with relevant national regulations when using artificial intelligence in areas such as public services and public administration.

Other artificial intelligence developers, providers, and users are encouraged to establish AI Ethics Review Committees based on actual circumstances.

ARTICLE 43 – OBLIGATIONS OF STATE ORGANS IN PROVISION AND DEVELOPMENT

State organs and other organizations legally endowed with the function of managing public affairs, when developing and providing artificial intelligence in fields such as governmental services and public administration, shall comply with the obligations of AI developers and providers as stipulated by this law, particularly ensuring the safety, transparency, and fairness of AI used in the management of public affairs.

ARTICLE 44 – AUTHORIZED REPRESENTATIVES

AI developers and providers located outside the People's Republic of China, as specified in Article 2, Section 2 of this law, must establish specialized institutions or designate representatives within the territory of the People's Republic of China to handle AI-related affairs. They must also submit the names of these institutions or the names and contact details of the representatives to the National AI Administrative Authority.

SECTION 2: OBLIGATIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE DEVELOPERS

ARTICLE 45 – ENHANCED OBLIGATIONS FOR AI DEVELOPERS ON THE NEGATIVE LIST

AI developers falling under the Negative List are obligated to comply with the following requirements:

- a. *Develop and maintain technical documentation that meets the requirements of this law;*
- b. *During the R&D process, establish and operate a quality management system that conforms to the requirements of this law, and cooperate with providers in fulfilling relevant duties;*
- c. *Cooperate with providers in fulfilling relevant duties;*
- d. *Comply with other obligations as stipulated by laws and administrative regulations.*

ARTICLE 46 – SPECIAL OBLIGATIONS FOR DEVELOPERS OF FOUNDATION MODELS

Developers of foundation models should abide by the following requirements:

1. ***Security and Risk Management:*** *Establish and maintain a robust security risk management system in accordance with national regulations, promptly and effectively preventing, monitoring, and handling risks that may affect national security, public interests, or the legitimate rights and interests of individuals, organizations, and economic order.*
2. ***Model and Data Stewardship:*** *Establish and maintain a comprehensive model and data stewardship system for foundational models in accordance with national regulations.*
3. ***Openness, Fairness, and Justice Principles:*** *Follow the principles of openness, fairness, and justice in formulating usage rules for foundational models, clarifying the obligations of developers and providers of foundational models, and preventing the abuse of market dominance.*
4. ***Compute:*** *Ensure the investment of computing resources necessary for managing safety/security risks.*

5. **Assistance:** Assist other developers and providers in fulfilling their obligations as specified by this law.
6. **Sanctions for Violations:** For developers and providers who seriously violate the provisions of this law, take necessary measures such as suspending services.
7. **Public Oversight:** Establish an independent institution mainly composed of external members to supervise the development of foundational models; publish an annual social responsibility report and accept public supervision.

SECTION 3: OBLIGATIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE PROVIDERS

ARTICLE 47 – REGISTRY OBLIGATIONS

AI providers offering products or services not listed on the negative list, with registered user numbers exceeding one million, should, within ten working days from the date of meeting the conditions, register the following information with the National AI Administrative Authority:

- a. **Contact Information:** Name or business name and contact details of the AI provider.
- b. **Details of AI Product/Service:** Trademarks or names, the form of provision, application areas, algorithm types, and a self-assessment report on security.
- c. **Content to be Publicized in the Record:** Information that is intended to be made public as part of the registration.
- d. **Other Information:** Any other information required by laws or administrative regulations.

Those with registered user numbers exceeding ten thousand but less than one million should, within ten working days from the date of meeting the conditions, register the aforementioned information with the provincial-level authority in charge of artificial intelligence.

Should there be any changes to the registered information, they must be amended within ten working days from the date of the change.

AI providers that have completed the registry shall indicate the filing number in a prominent position on their websites, applications, etc., on which services are provided to the public.

ARTICLE 48 – REGISTRY PROCESS

Upon receiving the registration materials, if the materials are complete, the regulatory authority should register them within thirty working days, issue a registration number, and make a public announcement. If the materials are incomplete, the regulatory authority must notify the registrant to provide additional materials within ten working days.

ARTICLE 49 – INTERNAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

AI providers should take the following measures to ensure that AI complies with laws and administrative regulations:

- a. Establish internal systems and corresponding operational procedures for data security, risk control, and quality management;*
- b. Keep logs automatically generated during the provision of AI products and services;*
- c. Regularly conduct education and training for employees;*
- d. Adopt compliant technical measures to ensure robustness and resistance to attacks;*
- e. Conduct an AI audit at least every two years;*
- f. Other measures as stipulated by laws and administrative regulations.*

ARTICLE 50 – TERMINATION MECHANISM

When an AI provider terminates the provision of products or services, the following appropriate arrangements should be made:

- a. Publicize the termination plan and user rights at least 30 working days in advance;*
- b. Delete users' personal information within 30 working days from the date of termination. According to relevant national regulations, necessary handling of data generated during the provision of AI products and services, training data, and algorithmic models should be carried out;*
- c. Other measures as stipulated by laws and administrative regulations.*

ARTICLE 51 – PERMISSION REVOCATION

AI providers within the Negative List should notify the competent authority at least 30 working days in advance, providing relevant details, and return the license to the original licensing authority after terminating the service.

AI providers outside the Negative List should complete the procedures for revoking the registry within 20 working days from the date of terminating the service.

ARTICLE 52 – ENHANCED OBLIGATIONS FOR NEGATIVE-LISTED AI PROVIDERS

AI providers within the scope of the Negative List shall also fulfill the following obligations:

- a. Conduct safety/security assessments in accordance with the requirements of this law to ensure that operations are safe and robust;*
- b. Develop and retain technical documentation that complies with the requirements of this law, to demonstrate that the provided AI systems meet the law's stipulations for AI systems on the Negative List;*
- c. Establish and operate a full-lifecycle quality management system that conforms to the requirements of this law;*
- d. Ensure that during the autonomous operation of AI products and services, humans have the ability to intervene or take control at any time;*
- e. Other obligations stipulated by laws or administrative regulations.*

ARTICLE 53 – OBLIGATIONS OF PLATFORM OPERATORS

If operators of online platforms are aware, or should be aware, that providers of products or services on the platform engage in AI provision through the platform, they should legally establish or amend their terms of service and transaction rules. They must clarify the standards and obligations for providers of products or services on the platform that offer artificial intelligence, ensuring that these providers do not abuse a dominant market position.

CHAPTER V

COMPREHENSIVE AI GOVERNANCE MECHANISM

ARTICLE 54 – RESPONSIBILITIES OF THE NATIONAL AI ADMINISTRATIVE AUTHORITY

The National AI Administrative Authority shall exercise the following administrative responsibilities for AI in accordance with the law:

- 1. Submit a special report on the development and governance of AI to the State Council by March 31 of each year;*
- 2. Conduct education and promotion for AI ethics and safety, and provide guidance and supervision for the development, provision, and usage of AI;*
- 3. Formulate AI regulatory rules and guidelines, and organize the development of standards concerning AI ethics, safety, and management;*
- 4. Promote the construction of a socialized service system for artificial intelligence governance, guide and support professional institutions in*

- providing services such as artificial intelligence safety/security monitoring, evaluation, auditing, and certification;*
5. *Guide and support the activities of the Open-Source Artificial Intelligence Foundations;*
 6. *Establish an artificial intelligence risk monitoring and early-warning mechanism, and organize the acquisition, analysis, research and early-warning of risk information in the field of artificial intelligence;*
 7. *Establish an emergency response mechanism for AI safety incidents;*
 8. *Receive and handle complaints and reports related to the development, provision, and usage of AI technologies and products;*
 9. *Investigate and address unlawful activities in the development, provision, and usage of AI;*
 10. *Other responsibilities stipulated by laws or administrative regulations.*

ARTICLE 55 – COMMITTEE OF EXPERTS ON AI ETHICS

The National AI Administrative Authority shall establish a National Committee of Experts on AI Ethics, while local regulatory authorities for artificial intelligence shall establish corresponding Committees of Experts on AI Ethics at their respective levels.

The National Committee of Experts on AI Ethics is tasked with researching major ethical issues related to the R&D, provision and use of artificial intelligence. It provides advisory opinions to the National AI Administrative Authority and guides the work pertaining to ethical review nationwide.

The local Committees of Experts on AI Ethics shall conduct research on ethical issues arising from the R&D, provision, and use of artificial intelligence within its administrative region, provide advisory opinions to the local competent artificial intelligence authorities at the corresponding levels, guide the work of artificial intelligence ethics review committees of developers, providers, and users within its administrative region, and be directly responsible for ethical reviews of activities involving the R&D, provision, and use of artificial intelligence in areas such as public services and public administration within its administrative region.

ARTICLE 56 – SECURITY REVIEW SYSTEM

Those engaged in the R&D, provision and use of artificial intelligence that impacts or may impact national security shall undergo a security review in accordance with relevant national regulations.

Decisions made in accordance with the security review process specified in laws shall be considered final.

ARTICLE 57 – TIMEFRAME FOR PRELIMINARY PROCEDURES

When AI developers, providers, or users apply for safety/security reviews, registries, or administrative licenses for new artificial intelligence technologies or applications in accordance with this Law and relevant national regulations, the National AI Administrative Authority shall process and respond within the prescribed timeframe.

ARTICLE 58 – INTERVIEWING

If the National AI Administrative Authority and local AI administrative authorities at all levels, in the course of fulfilling their responsibilities, discover that activities related to the R&D or provision of AI pose significant risks or have resulted in safety/security incidents, they may, in accordance with specified authorities and procedures, interview the relevant AI developers or providers and require them to take the following measures:

- a. Implement corrective actions as specified to eliminate potential risks;*
- b. Provide an appropriate explanation of their R&D, and provisioning activities, clarify responsibilities related to the development, management, and operation of AI services, discuss measures taken to ensure fairness, safety, and stability, and assess the impact on stakeholders;*
- c. Commission a professional organization to conduct a compliance audit of their AI R&D and provisioning activities.*

If AI developers and providers commit to timely corrective actions to achieve compliance, and can effectively avoid causing harm through their AI R&D, provision, or usage activities, they may not be required to suspend relevant activities. However, if the National AI Administrative Authority deems that potential harm may occur, it may order the suspension of such activities.

ARTICLE 59 – INNOVATIVE REGULATION

In cases where minor violations occur in the activities related to the R&D, provision, and use of AI, and the decides not to administer administrative penalties according to the law, the Authority should adopt measures such as criticism and education, guidance interviews, and organizing consultative meetings to encourage the parties involved to conduct their activities – R&D, provision, and use in the AI industrialization in a lawful and compliant manner.

The National AI Administrative Authority shall formulate dedicated compliance guidelines for open-source artificial intelligence developers, promoting the innovative development of open-source artificial intelligence.

ARTICLE 60 – REGULATORY SANDBOX

The National AI Administrative Authority shall establish an AI regulatory experimental mechanism and issue specific regulations and guidelines concerning the following matters:

- a. Conditions for participating in the regulatory experimentation;*
- b. Operational mechanisms of the regulatory experimentation;*
- c. Risk monitoring and prevention measures in the regulatory experimentation;*
- d. Obligations and liability reduction mechanisms for AI developers and providers participating in the regulatory experimentation.*

ARTICLE 61 – OFFICIALS RESPONSIBLE FOR STATE ORGANS

State organs and other organizations, which are legally endowed with the management of public affairs, shall designate individuals responsible for artificial intelligence. These appointed persons are tasked with supervising the use of artificial intelligence and the implementation of safety protection measures.

ARTICLE 62 – LAW ENFORCEMENT

The National AI Administrative Authority should enhance the development of specialized teams and specialized technology, improve the staff’s professional capabilities, conduct relevant technical training, and continuously elevate the capability and standard of AI regulation.

Furthermore, the National AI Administrative Authority should, in accordance with the law, establish administrative enforcement procedures specific to its system and set up a system for supervising administrative enforcement.

ARTICLE 63 – GOVERNANCE THROUGH TECHNOLOGY

The State shall support enterprises, research institutions, and other organizations in researching and developing technologies related to AI monitoring and early warning, safety/security assessment, and emergency response. It encourages the application of regulatory technology (RegTech) and compliance technology (ComplianceTech) in the field of artificial intelligence.

ARTICLE 64 – COUNTERMEASURES AGAINST FOREIGN ENTITIES

Where overseas organizations or individuals engage in AI R&D, provision, or usage activities that infringe upon the legitimate rights and interests of citizens of the People’s Republic of China, or endanger the national security or public interests of the People’s Republic of China, the National AI Administrative Authority may, in accordance with the law, adopt measures to restrict or prohibit their AI R&D, provision, or usage activities within the territory of the People’s Republic of China and shall make public announcements thereof.

ARTICLE 65 – RECIPROCAL MEASURES

If any country or region adopts discriminatory prohibitions, restrictions, or similar measures against the People’s Republic of China in aspects related to AI R&D, investment, trade, etc., the People’s Republic of China may take reciprocal measures against that country or region based on the actual circumstances.

CHAPTER VI

LIABILITIES

ARTICLE 66 – GENERAL LIABILITIES

For violations of the provisions of this law in conducting R&D and provision activities, the National AI Administrative Authority shall order corrections, issue warnings, confiscate unlawful gains, and order the suspension or termination of relevant operations. Those who refuse to correct the violations shall be fined up to one million yuan; the directly responsible supervisors and other personnel directly liable shall be fined between ten thousand and one hundred thousand yuan.

For violations as specified in the preceding paragraph that are severe, the National AI Administrative Authority shall order corrections, confiscate unlawful gains, and impose a fine of up to ten million yuan or up to four percent of the previous year's turnover. The Authority may also order the suspension of relevant operations, or issue orders for business rectification, or notify relevant supervisory authorities to revoke the relevant business license or business operation permit. Fines of between one hundred thousand and one million yuan shall be imposed on the directly responsible supervisors and other personnel directly liable.

ARTICLE 67 – REVOCATION OF NEGATIVE-LIST LICENSES

Where an artificial intelligence developer or provider violates the provisions of this Law during R&D or provision activities, resulting in a significant safety/security incident,

multiple safety/security incidents, or multiple administrative penalties, the National AI Administrative Authority may suspend the license and order rectification within a prescribed period; if rectification is not made upon the expiration of the period, or if a safety/security incident occurs again or an administrative penalty is imposed after the suspension of the license, the National AI Administrative Authority may revoke the license.

ARTICLE 68 – DISCRETIONARY METHODS FOR ADMINISTRATIVE FINES

Fines stipulated in this law may serve as a supplement to or substitute for corrective measures. When the National AI Administrative Authority determines the amount of an administrative fine, it shall adhere to the principles of legality, proportionality, fairness and justice, integration of punishment and education, and comprehensive discretion. The following factors should be fully considered:

- 1. The nature, severity, duration, and impact of the violation, as well as the extent and degree of damage caused;*
- 2. Whether the violation was intentional or negligent;*
- 3. Whether remedial measures have been taken to mitigate the potential loss caused by the violation;*
- 4. Whether the National AI Administrative Authority was notified in accordance with the provisions of this law;*
- 5. Whether reasonable and effective organizational and technical measures have been taken to manage the risks of AI in accordance with this law;*
- 6. Whether compliance with AI and safety-related standards has been achieved or relevant certifications have been obtained;*
- 7. Prior violations;*
- 8. Other factors stipulated by laws and regulations that may aggravate or mitigate the penalty.*

ARTICLE 69 – LIABILITY FOR REGISTRY VIOLATIONS

If an AI provider is required to file a registry but fails to do so, the National AI Administrative Authority shall issue a warning. In severe cases, a fine between ten thousand and one hundred thousand yuan may be imposed.

If an AI provider obtains registry through improper means, such as concealing relevant information or providing false materials, the National AI Administrative Authority shall revoke the registry, issue a warning, and make a public criticism. In severe cases, a fine between one hundred thousand and one million yuan may be imposed.

If an AI provider terminates its service without going through the procedures to cancel the registry, or if it is subjected to administrative penalties such as being ordered to shut down the website, having its relevant business permit revoked, or having its operation license revoked due to serious legal violations, the National AI Administrative Authority shall cancel the registry.

ARTICLE 70 – CIVIL TORT LIABILITY

If the R&D or provision of AI infringes on individual rights and causes damage, the developer or provider shall bear tort liability, such as compensation for damages, except where the developer and provider can prove they are not at fault.

The compensation liability mentioned in the preceding paragraph is determined based on the loss suffered by the user or the affected individual or organization, or the benefits obtained by the developer or provider as a result of this. If the loss suffered by the user or the affected individual or organization and the benefit gained by the provider are difficult to determine, the amount of compensation will be determined based on the actual case.

If a provider is aware or should have been aware that a user is infringing upon others' intellectual property rights by utilizing the products or services provided, and the provider fails to take necessary measures, the provider shall bear joint and several liability with the user. A provider shall not bear joint and several liability with the user if there is evidence that the following measures have been taken:

- a. Necessary identification has been made for artificial intelligence-generated content;*
- b. Users have been reminded through user agreements or other means not to infringe upon others' intellectual property rights;*
- c. Rules for intellectual property protection have been established, and upon discovery of a user infringing upon others' intellectual property rights by utilizing generative artificial intelligence services, warning, functional restriction, suspension, or termination of service provision to the user and other dispositive measures have been taken in accordance with laws and agreements;*

d. A mechanism for intellectual property rights complaints has been established.

ARTICLE 71 – LIABILITY EXEMPTION FOR OPEN-SOURCE AI

Those who provide part of the code modules needed for the R&D of artificial intelligence for free and in an open-source manner, and who clearly disclose its functions and safety/security risks, shall not bear legal liability.

Individuals or organizations that provide artificial intelligence in a free-and-open-source manner can have their legal liability reduced or exempted if they can prove that they have established an artificial intelligence compliance governance system that meets national standards and have taken corresponding safety measures.

ARTICLE 72 – LEGAL REDRESS

Citizens, legal persons, or other organizations that disagree with the administrative actions taken by the competent authorities for artificial intelligence may apply for administrative reconsideration or file an administrative lawsuit in a People’s Court in accordance with the law.

ARTICLE 73 – PUBLIC INTEREST LITIGATION

Where an artificial intelligence provider violates the provisions of this Law by providing products or services that infringe upon the rights and interests of numerous individuals, the People’s Procuratorates, consumer organizations stipulated by law, and organizations designated by the National AI Administrative Authority may file lawsuits with the People’s Courts in accordance with the law.

ARTICLE 74 – THE INTERFACE BETWEEN ADMINISTRATIVE PENALTIES AND CRIMINAL LIABILITIES

Violations of the provisions of this law that constitute violations of public security administration shall be punished in accordance with the law. If a crime is constituted, criminal liability shall be pursued in accordance with the law.

ARTICLE 75 – POST-COMPLIANCE NON-PROSECUTION

If AI developers or providers violate the provisions of this Law and bear administrative liability, where the compliance system of the subject entity is evaluated to meet the

effectiveness standards, they shall be exempted from penalties or given mitigated penalties in accordance with the law.

If a violation of the provisions of this Law constitutes a crime, where the compliance system of the subject entity involved is evaluated to meet the effectiveness standards, the People's Procuratorates may, by referring to the evaluation conclusions, make decisions in accordance with the law not to approve arrest, change compulsory measures, or not to prosecute, propose sentencing recommendations for lenient punishment, or submit procuratorial opinions to relevant competent authorities for lenient penalties or disciplinary actions.

ARTICLE 76 – LIABILITY FOR FAILURE TO PERFORM OBLIGATIONS BY STATE ORGANS

State organs engaged in the R&D, provision, and use of artificial intelligence shall strictly comply with the obligations defined by this law. Failure to perform the obligations stipulated by this law shall be corrected by its higher-level organ or the National AI Administrative Authority; legal disciplinary action shall be taken against those directly in charge and other directly responsible personnel.

State employees who neglect their duties, abuse their powers, or engage in corruption without constituting a crime shall be disciplined in accordance with the law.

In cases that do not constitute by-law faults of administrative enforcement, the administrative enforcement liability of relevant personnel will not be pursued.

CHAPTER VII

SUPPLEMENTARY

PROVISIONS

ARTICLE 77 – MILITARY ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

The regulations governing the R&D, provision, and use of artificial intelligence by the Chinese People’s Liberation Army and the Chinese People’s Armed Police Force shall be separately stipulated by the Central Military Commission in accordance with the principles prescribed in this Law.

ARTICLE 78 – DEFINITIONS

The following terms in this law have the definitions as described below:

- a. *Artificial Intelligence* refers to automated systems that operate with a certain level of autonomy, serving specific or general objectives and capable of affecting physical or virtual environments through prediction, recommendation, or decision-making. This includes data, features, models, service provision interfaces, and embedded terminal devices.

- b. *Artificial Intelligence Developers* refer to individuals or organizations solely engaged in activities such as algorithm design, training data labeling, feature extraction, model training and optimization, testing deployment, and the free and open-source provision during artificial intelligence research and development.
- c. *Artificial Intelligence Providers* refer to individuals or organizations that provide AI or related technical support for commercial purposes, or regardless of commercial intent, offer AI or related technical support to the public. This does not include individuals or organizations that provide AI for free and as open-source.
- d. *Artificial Intelligence Users* refer to individuals or organizations that utilize AI according to its capabilities and purposes.
- e. *Foundation Models* refer to artificial intelligence models that have undergone training with the accumulation of computing power investment to a certain scale, serving general purposes, and capable of providing technological support for a wide range of downstream services. The floating-point operations (FLOPs) and other computing power standards for the identification of foundation models shall be formulated, publicly issued, and regularly updated by the National AI Administrative Authority.

ARTICLE 79 – IMPLEMENTATION DATE

This law shall come into effect on [Day] [Month] [Year].

ARTICLE 80 – NEGATIVE-LIST DISCLOSURE SYSTEM

The National AI Administrative Authority shall publish the Artificial Intelligence Negative List no later than six months before the implementation of this law, and promptly make it public after periodic updates.